

OBSEA Data Management Plan

Version 1.0

EMSO ERIC
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History of changes

Version	Date	Change	Author(s)
1.0	21/12/2023	First version	Enoc Martínez

OBSEA Data Management Plan

Data Collection
What data will you collect or create?
<p>Type of data: OBSEA collects a wide variety of oceanographic data (see list below) in real-time. Mainly stored as time-series data, but in some cases using domain-specific formats (WAVs, JPEG, etc.). Datasets are generated by sensors.</p> <p>Volume of data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Time-series: from 2011-2023 around 250 million data points in a centralised database (~26 GB) with an increment of 35 million data points / year WAV data: 6 TB since 2020 (16GB / day) Pictures: around 100 GB of pictures since 2010 <p>Type of storage:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> timeseries: data we use PostgresQL + TimescaleDB database. Periodic exports to CSV / netCDF images: we use a regular UNIX filesystem with pics organised in year/month/day tree WAVs: a regular UNIX filesystem with pics organised in year/month/day tree Video and seismology: TBD (currently using an obsolete infrastructure) <p>List of parameters (time-series data):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> sea water temperature sea water pressure sea water electrical conductivity sea water salinity speed of sound in sea water sound pressure level sea water speed sea water direction wave height wave direction wave period air temperature air pressure wind direction wind speed saturation of oxygen in sea water sea water oxidation reduction potential sea water turbidity sea water pH coloured dissolved organic matter crude oil refined fuels

Other parameters:

- underwater sound (WAV files)
- underwater pictures (JPEG files)
- underwater video (MP4 files)
- seismic data (miniSEED files)

How will the data be collected or created?

Data comes to a shore station in real-time. At the shore station there are two different workflows: one for standard time-series (CTD, ADCP, etc.) data and the other for file-based data (pictures, hydrophones, seismology).

The time-series data is parsed, quality controlled (currently [QARTOD](#) flags) and stored into a PostgreSQL/[TimescaleDB](#) database, connected to an [OGC SensorThing API](#). A resampling process is periodically executed (crontab) to generate an averaged time-series (generally 30min), which are stored in a regular PostgreSQL table (Sensorthings OBSERVATIONS table). The [FROST](#) implementation of the SensorThings API standard is currently used, however the database has been customised with a [TimescaleDB hypertable](#) to store large amounts of time-series data.

The file-based data is acquired by custom scripts and archived in a regular UNIX filesystem in a file tree following a YEAR/MONTH/DAY/<daily files> pattern.

To access the data there are 3 mechanisms: SensorThings API, ERDDAP and CKAN. For every time-series sensor two different datasets are generated, one with the full data and another with the 30min averages. This applies to all data interfaces.

The SensorThings API is exposed publicly and anyone can query it for (meta)data using its standard REST API.

The data is ingested into the ERDDAP in near-realtime (exported to CSV every 30min and ERDDAP reloads datasets every 15min). WAV and JPEG files are sent to ERDDAP as soon as they are generated. From the ERDDAP interface it is possible to download the data in CSV, netCDF and many other file formats. Of course, metadata and QC flags are also ingested into ERDDAP.

Time-series data is exported in yearly files and ingested into a self-hosted CKAN repository, which also exposes a RDF-DCAT catalogue.

For data visualisation there's the OBSEA web page and also a Grafana service with a set of dashboards that can be anonymously accessed..

Documentation and Metadata

What documentation and metadata will accompany the data?

Metadata is centralised in the SensorThings database, and then propagated to ERDDAP and CKAN. Metadata fields include generic metadata (title, summary, processing level info, owner, coordinates, PI, data curator, time-coverage) and sensor-specific metadata (model, manufacturer, serial number, type of sensor, deployment depth, etc.).

Parameters are identified using the OceanSites 4-character codes (and P02 in NVS in case they are not explicitly declared in OceanSites data guide). In some specific cases copernicus 4-character codes are used. All parameters have a standard name (following Climate and Forecast standard) and a NVS P01 parameter code.

Sensors are defined (when possible) using L22 device code, the L05 device type code and the L35 manufacturer code.

Involved institutions are referenced using ROR and/or EDMO codes.

Ethics and Legal Compliance

How will you manage any ethical issues?

No ethical GDPR issues detected so far,

How will you manage copyright and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues?

All data is owned by UPC, openly available under a CC-BY licence. Data is published in real-time (SensorThings API / ERDDAP) and organised in yearly datasets (CKAN).

Storage and Backup

How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?

The main database (PostgresQL) is backed up on a daily basis. All services (except PostgresQL database) are dockerized, so the docker volumes and docker-compose files are backed up on a daily basis.

Daily backups are stored at cloud resources provided by EGI (currently CESGA). Additionally a weekly copy of the backups is stored in a self-hosted server at UPC to ensure geo-distributed backups.

Redeployment of services is trivial using docker-compose files and the volume backups. The redeployment of the whole infrastructure should take less than one day. Periodic recoveries are performed to ensure that backups are consistent.

Due to the huge volume, hydrophone data is currently not being backed up (needs to be explored).

Responsible for backup and recovery: Enoc Martínez

Right now we do have enough storage space to store the backups in the long term (except hydrophone data). We expect to have enough resources to maintain the cyber-infrastructure in the long-term since the estimated cost is relatively low (less than 5K a year) and there is institutional support from EGI. But, of course, it will depend on the available funding.

How will you manage access and security?
All data is stored in Linux servers, only accessible through SSH. The data services only provide read permissions to the data. All our data is transmitted in real-time through a private LAN.

Selection and Preservation
Which data are of long term value and should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?
We plan to retain ALL time-series and image data in the long-term in our infrastructure. All time-series data is shared with EMSO ERIC data services and also with MonGOOS (and forwarded to Copernicus and EMODnet). The main risk is to be able to retain WAV data in the long-term due to its high volume (6 TB + 16 GB per day).
What is the long-term preservation plan for the dataset?
The plan is to host the data internally in our repository (CKAN). Additionally data is being shared with domain-relevant data aggregators such as MonGOOS, EMODnet and Copernicus.

Data Sharing
How will you share the data?
Data is shared in near real-time through ERDDAP into MonGOOS, Copernicus and EMODnet in addition to our own infrastructure. All data has CC-BY licensing to ensure reusability.
Are any restrictions on data sharing required?
NO

Responsibilities and Resources
Who will be responsible for data management?
Data Manager / Data Curator / Cloud System Administrator: Enoc Martínez Self-hosted systems administrator: Javier Cadena Sensor operators: Marc Nogueras, Daniel M. Toma, Matias Carandell PI: Joaquín del Río

What resources will you require to deliver your plan?
Human resources: at least one full-time IT specialist with extensive knowledge of the following technologies: Linux, Docker, ERDDAP, CKAN, SensorThings, Git, python3, Grafana, OpenStack, Zabbix, PostgreSQL and TimescaleDB. So far no charges applied by data repositories. Estimated cost of 5K€ year for the hosting of the cyber-infrastructure.